

Grant Agreement No: 951754

FCCIS

Future Circular Collider Innovation Study

Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Research and Innovation Action

DELIVERABLE REPORT

EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PARTICLE COLLIDER KEY PERFORMANCE ENABLERS

Document identifier:	FCCIS-P3-WP2-D7
Due date:	End of Month 42 (May 2024)
Date:	24/06/2024
Work package/unit:	WP2 Collider Design
Organisation:	DESY
Version:	V1.0
Status:	RELEASED
Keywords:	Collider characterisations, summary report

Abstract:

A report summarising the results from the experimental verifications of performance enabling techniques at various accelerators. Analysis of the beam-beam behaviour for the crab waist collision scheme and possibly, its sensitivity to various optics aberrations at the collision point.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 951754.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Organisation	Date
Authored by	Ilya Agapov Frank Zimmermann	DESY CERN	18/06/2024
Edited by	Julie Hadre	CERN	19/06/2024
Approved by	Michael Benedikt	CERN	21/06/2024

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Experimental Characterisations of Particle Collider Key Performance Enablers

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Abstract

We summarize the status and future plans for the experimental verification of various FCC-ee performance-enabling techniques. The beam tests and analysis of experimental and operational aspects of running colliders are supported by FCCIS, the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 951754.

Keywords

FCCIS Deliverable D2.4

1 Preamble

In this report, we review the status and future plans for the experimental demonstration of several key FCC-ee performance-enabling techniques, as well as analysis of experimental and operational aspects of running colliders with focus on SuperKEKB. Beam tests were performed at KARA (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany), at PETRA III (DESY Hamburg) and at ESRF-EBS (Grenoble, France). Delays and gaps in the SuperKEKB schedule prevented almost all of the dedicated machine studies which had finally been planned for 2024, but operational data and achieved performance are analyzed.

2 Introduction

The proposed FCC-ee collider [1] is a key component of the vision for a possible integrated research programme probing energy scales up to 100 TeV energy, that would span the whole of the XXI century (see e.g. [2]). The goal of FCC-ee is to perform precision measurements at the W, Z, (Z) Higgs, and $t\bar{t}$ energies, create the bulk of the civil infrastructure for the 100 TeV collider, and leave time for further R&D into high-field superconducting magnets, that is still required for the hh machine, at the same time seamlessly continuing CERN's physics programme beyond the high luminosity (HL) LHC upgrade.

The FCC-ee machine and detectors are based on established concepts and benefit from decades of development of circular electron storage rings for collider and for synchrotron light applications. While FCC-ee builds on proven technology, it pushes the performance parameters (see Table 1) [3, 4]. The ultimate goal of a factory type machine is to achieve maximum possible (integrated) luminosity. For the so-called nanobeam scheme the instantaneous is

$$L = \frac{N_+ N_- n_b f_0}{2\pi \phi_x \Sigma_z \Sigma_y^*}, \quad (1)$$

where N_{\pm} denotes the number of particles of each species per bunch, n_b the number of bunches per beam, ϕ_x half the crossing angle, f_0 the revolution frequency, and

$$\Sigma_z = \sqrt{\sigma_{z+}^2 + \sigma_{z-}^2} \quad \Sigma_y^* = \sqrt{\sigma_{y+}^{*2} + \sigma_{y-}^{*2}}$$

The most important constraint relates to the so-called beam-beam parameter

$$\xi_{\pm} \approx \frac{r_e N_{\pm}}{2\pi \gamma_{\pm}} \frac{1}{\phi_x \sigma_z} \sqrt{\frac{\beta_y^*}{\epsilon_y}} = 2er_e \frac{L \beta_y^*}{\gamma_{\pm} I_{\pm}}. \quad (2)$$

The luminosity is essentially determined by three parameters: beam-beam parameter, beam current, and the vertical beta function at the interaction point

$$L \propto \frac{\xi_y I}{\beta_y^*}$$

The beam-beam parameter is roughly the beam-beam induced tune shift, and is thus limited (by the space available for the tune footprint to avoid detrimental resonances). The maximum beam-beam parameters ever achieved are around 0.09 (LEP, KEK). For round beam collisions, even higher parameters could be reached at VEPP2000, though the exact value (varying between 0.08 and 0.17) depended on the definition or measurement technique [5]. For FCC-ee, as for many other classical e^+e^- colliders, flat beams can achieve higher luminosity than round beam collisions. In the case of flat colliding, the crab waist collision scheme can increase the beam-beam limit by about a factor of 2, as was demonstrated at DAΦNE [6]. From the luminosity scaling it can be seen that large crossing angle and long bunches (or large Piwinski angle $\varphi \approx \sigma_z \phi_x / \sigma_x^*$) allows increasing the beam current and/or reducing the vertical beta function, even for constant beam-beam parameter value, thus resulting in further luminosity gains.

The beam currents are often limited by collective instabilities, thermal load on components, and beam-induced backgrounds. Light sources typically operate at beam currents between one and several hundreds mA. B factories reach higher currents of several A. In this respect, the FCC-ee parameters, most aggressive at the Z energy with about 1.3 A, are relatively conservative. The FCC-ee beam current is defined by setting a limit of 50 MW for the synchrotron radiation power emitted per beam.

The beta function at the interaction point (IP) is pushed to the limit in the nanobeam crab waist scheme, Other challenges associated with the FCC-ee design include:

- Sheer number of components and the size of the facility, that requires putting focus on cost and energy efficiency
- Extreme parameters of beam-beam interaction (so-called beamstrahlung and excitation of nonlinear resonances)
- Need for precise energy calibration

Table 1: Parameters of the FCC-ee lattices at various energies

Beam energy [GeV]	45.6 (Z)	80 (W)	120 (ZH)	182.5 ($t\bar{t}$)
ε_x in collision [nm]	0.71	2.17	0.67	1.57
ε_y in collision [pm]	1.9	2.2	1.0	1.6
Bunch length σ_z in collision [mm]	15.5	5	5	2.3
$\xi_{x,y}$	0.02/0.1	0.013/0.13	0.01/0.09	0.06/0.15
$L / IP [10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}]$	141	20	6.3	1.4

^a Status 15 Nov. 2023. <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1326738/>

The FCC Feasibility Study and FCCIS support experimental tests and exchange of experience with latest-generation electron storage rings. Experience is also gained at two existing e^+e^- colliders, DAΦNE and SuperKEKB, at dedicated test facilities such as KARA, and at a number of operational synchrotron radiation user facilities such as PETRA III.

In the following section, a number of experimental test results are discussed. It has to be noted that the pandemic, increased energy prices, inflation and the Ukraine war influenced operation and project execution schedules of almost all laboratories worldwide, and rendered some facilities such as those

Table 2: Parameters for some existing lepton storage rings

Facility	SuperKEKB	DAΦNE	PETRAIII	EBS
E [GeV]	4/7	0.5	6	6
Circumference [m]	3016.3	97	2304	844
Current [A] design (achieved)	3.6/2.6 (1.3/1.1)	2.4/1.4	0.12	0.2
ε_x [nm] design (achieved)	3.2/4.6 (4.0/4.6)	260	1.4	0.13
ε_y [pm] design (achieved)	9/13 (38/31)	2.6	10	5
β_x^* [mm] design (achieved)	32/25 (80/60)	260	1200	6900
β_y^* [mm] design (achieved)	0.27/0.3 (1/0.8)	9	2300	2700
L/IP [$10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$] design (achieved)	80 (4.7)	0.04	-	-

at BINP¹ unavailable for European users. This had a significant impact on the FCC-ee experimental verification programme, which had to be readjusted and, to some extent, delayed. The programme is continuing. More conclusive results are to be expected by the time of the next European Particle Physics Strategy update in 2025–2026.

In this report, we report on tests and experience in the following areas:

- Optics correction and tuning
- Tests of some diagnostics performance
- Energy calibration
- Experience with colliders utilizing the crab-waist collision scheme, in particular SuperKEKB
- Radiofrequency (RF) cavities operated in reverse phase mode, developed for SuperKEKB and tested at the former KEKB.

Beam tests at KARA, PETRA III and ESRF-EBS are discussed in Section 3 and operational experience of SuperKEKB in Section 4. For comparison, the parameters of modern electron storage rings that provide relevant expertise and can serve for tests are listed in Table 2.

3 Tests and analysis of performance-enabling techniques

3.1 Optics corrections and tuning

In recent decades, significant progress with optics tuning and correction to address both correction precision and optics complexity has been achieved, mostly in the connection with the LHC [7] and with the emergence of fourth-generation light sources. Typical fourth-generation light sources cannot reach the level of mechanical alignment sufficient to guarantee a stable closed orbit. With the realistically achievable initial mechanical alignment levels of about $30 \mu\text{m}$, a sequence of procedures is required to establish a circulating beam and target parameters such as the emittance and the lifetime. This sequence typically consists of the first-turn threading, the trajectory-based beam-based alignment, by determining the BPM readings corresponding to the centres of nearby magnets, adjusting the RF system frequencies and phases, establishing stored beam, orbit correction, and, finally, dispersion, beta-beat and coupling correction. After the last step, target emittances and beam lifetimes can usually be achieved. Software to perform such machine startup and tuning has been developed and tested [8–10]. Startup and correction procedures were employed, for example, in the commissioning of the EBS at ESRF. Commissioning of a significant number of fourth-generation light sources in the coming years will rely on this software. Beam lifetime and injection efficiency can then further be improved in the course of machine opera-

¹BINP hosts two out of five e^+e^- colliders presently operational worldwide, which were expected to be important test facilities.

tion, often with semi-empirical methods. Recently, fully-automatic tools for such tuning have become available [11].

The simulated commissioning tools for both ESRF-EBS and FCC-ee are based on the *pyAT* beam optics engine [12, 13]. Conversion of FCC-ee lattices into this framework were implemented and benchmarked, and lattice correction studies performed [14]. This allowed extending the initial error analysis and correction studies [15, 16]. Dedicated beam time (about 20 hours in total) at PETRA III was allocated to test the new correction framework. The first set of tests addressed the first turn steering algorithms. Here, the difficulty is mostly related to the robustness of the software to diagnostics errors, such as synchronization errors of BPMs. Procedures had to be developed to process the BPM ADC data to detect and possibly correct such errors. Thanks to these, a successful demonstration became possible.

The second set of tests was to demonstrate optics correction using the adapted OMC software from CERN [17]. PETRA III has the capability of horizontal and vertical AC beam excitation in a wide frequency range (up to 250 MHz) using the transverse multi-bunch feedback system. The tests demonstrated the applicability of the OMC software to electron beams with strong radiation damping (see Figure 1). Here, the challenges to be overcome were also related to BPM data quality: synchronization errors of BPMs had to be detected and corrected; bunch fill patterns that provide sufficient charge for good BPM resolution but avoid intensity-driven tune shifts or multibunch oscillations had to be found; signal amplifier gains providing best measurement had to be adjusted. Overall, the optics measurement based on AC excitation still remains an involved technique requiring significant system adjustment and data analysis. On the other hand, it can potentially provide on-line optics monitoring if both parameter setup and data analysis are sufficiently automated. These tests are being continued with improved correction procedures and refined lattice modelling.

Figure 1: Example results from an optics measurement based on AC excitation at PETRA III.

While light sources are similar to FCC-ee in terms of optics sensitivity of the arc magnets, a significant difference arises from the fact that the high luminosity of e^+e^- colliders is achieved, among other reasons, by an extreme β^* (mm to sub-mm) at the interaction point. For comparison, beta functions in the undulator insertions of light sources are typically of several meters in size. The small beta function at the collision point, β_y^* , generates a large vertical chromaticity in the interaction region (IR), which has to be locally compensated by sextupoles. The interaction region optics, together with the beam-

beam interaction, are major contributions to the machine nonlinearity, and pose complications to optics tuning and correction. At FCC-ee, the sensitivity of the optics to errors in the final focus quadrupoles is about two orders of magnitude higher than for the arc quadrupoles. First studies interfacing the optics correction chain with the *Lifetrac* code to evaluate the beam-beam performance in presence of realistic lattice nonlinearities were executed, assuming a reduced set of errors for the final focus magnets. A systematic analysis of the influence of optics aberrations at the IP on the luminosity performance and the development of more detailed procedures of IR (beam-based) alignment and tuning are planned for the future. Analysing the experience of SuperKEKB and reliable high-fidelity simulation tools using precise field error and alignment models will be essential for understanding the tunability of the IR. A next step could be attempting to reconstruct and model the SuperKEKB lattice including the actual orbit corrector settings, beam-position-monitor (BPM) readings, and other operational parameters.

3.2 Diagnostics

In terms of emittance and bunch length, FCC-ee is in the same range as the fourth-generation light sources. Some differences include: significantly higher total beam current at Z energies; significantly lower single bunch current at the $t\bar{t}$ energy (albeit with a high bunch charge at all energies); significantly higher critical energy of synchrotron radiation photons at $t\bar{t}$ energies; positions with extremely large beta functions in the collider lattice. The latter could potentially render the emittance diagnostics relatively relaxed, since its resolution depends on the beam size. Standard techniques such as interferometry and pinhole imaging can be applied. Both techniques are in routine operation at light sources, e.g. at PETRA III.

On a critical path to successful machine operation is guaranteeing sufficient BPM resolution, since this determines the precision of orbit control, first turn steering, optics measurement and correction, and beam-based alignment. While the requirements for FCC-ee are still being evaluated, they seem to be comparable to those of last generation light sources. For the PETRA upgrade project, the requirements were initially set to 20 μm for a single bunch (ca. 1 nC or 0.125 mA) single turn mode and 100 nm in the orbit mode for beam current of 200 mA. These requirements could not be achieved with the existing *Libera* system, and developments and tests of the next generation electronics became necessary. Figure 2 shows the turn-by-turn BPM resolution tests of various systems presented in [18]. Both the required turn-by-turn and orbit resolution can be provided by the newer generation of BPM systems. In addition, a long-term drift compensation, limiting slow changes to below 1 μm per week, was developed [19]. BPM electronics was implemented on the basis of the MTCA.4 platform [20]. These results can be extrapolated to the FCC-ee case by scaling with the beam pipe aperture (10 mm radius in the case of the PETRA upgrade) and BPM button size. Table 3 compares the BPM resolutions for single-pass single-bunch measurements and (average) orbit measurements assumed for FCC-ee, with those achieved or planned at various light sources and SuperKEKB.

Table 3: BPM resolution and related parameters at three existing and two future machines

Machine	ESRF-EBS	PETRA III	SuperKEKB	PETRA IV	FCC-ee-Z
beam pipe radius [mm]	10	20	45	10	30
bunch charge [nC]	0.03–17	1–20	10	0.8–10	2–30
rms bunch length [mm]	3	13	5	~ 3.5	5–15
single-pass resol. [μm]	10	60–70 (20)	200	< 10	< 5
average beam current [A]	0.2	0.1	1–3	0.08–0.2	1.3
orbit resolution [μm]	0.02–0.04	0.02–0.2	<3	0.1	0.1

Figure 2: Results of BPM resolution studies at PETRA III for different types of electronic processing systems. Monitor radius $K=10$ mm.

3.3 Polarimetry and energy calibration

Resonant depolarisation (RDP) has long been established as an energy calibration technique for e+e- colliders and some light sources [21–23]. It is of particular importance for precision measurement machines such as FCC-ee [24, 25]. A typical resolution of $\Delta E/E \approx 10^{-5}$ has been achieved at LEP and a record value of $\approx 10^{-6}$ at VEPP-4 [23]. One of the difficulties of applying this technique at FCC-ee, where it will be employed at Z and W energies, is the relatively long polarization times, even in the presence of special wiggler magnets. Understanding the influence of optics errors on the polarization process and benchmarking of simulation codes is important to guarantee constant and reliable energy calibration at FCC-ee. KARA provides a setup for energy calibration using RDP [26, 27], and its short polarisation times of the order of 10 minutes make it an ideal setting for tests. In 2023, two machine study shifts were performed to measure polarisation / depolarisation and to explore how the inferred beam energy is affected by the depolariser frequency scan speed and direction of the scan [28]. An example is shown in Fig. 3. Together with optics measurement data [29], the KARA RDP data will provide a basis for simulation benchmarks.

4 Experience with operating colliders

4.1 Crab-waist collisions

The crab-waist scheme tilts the waists of colliding bunches so that the transverse beam-beam resonances are suppressed [6, 30, 31]. This scheme was successfully implemented at DAΦNE. Beam-beam simulations agreed with experimentally determined beam parameters. More recently, SuperKEKB [32] has also implemented the crab-waist collision scheme [33]. Initial tests [34] showed that crab-waist operation indeed leads to significant luminosity increase and higher beam-beam tune shifts. No fundamental problems were encountered. The SuperKEKB beam currents and IP beta functions are presently limited by other effects, as discussed below, so that the full benefit of the crab waist could not yet be exploited.

Figure 3: Example RDP scan result at KARA for increasing (top) and decreasing depolariser frequency (bottom) with the respective fit results shown. The different shape of the fitted function is consistent with a downward drift in beam energy. [28].

4.2 Beam parameters achieved at SuperKEKB

SuperKEKB is the facility most closely resembling FCC-ee (nanobeam crab waist scheme, top-up operation) and its experience is a valuable input to the FCC feasibility study. The luminosity performance of SuperKEKB has as of yet been significantly below the design values. The achieved beam-beam parameters, emittances, and luminosity are shown in Figures 4, 5, and 6.

There are a number of reasons for the lower-than-design luminosity performance: larger than expected collimator impedance limiting the beam current, poorly understood sudden beam losses, and poorly understood emittance blowup in a transfer line, limiting the injector performance, as well as a small dynamic aperture. These factors contribute to reduced beam current, larger vertical emittance, and larger beta star at the IP, which together sums up to more than an order of magnitude lower luminosity than the design. While the progress is slow, in principle it is not unusual for a collider to take many years of tuning and adjustment to reach its design parameters. In general, the problems seem to arise more from mechanical flaws than from the conceptual beam optics design. Experience with performance tuning and dedicated beam dynamics studies in the coming years will shed more light on the challenges of FCC-ee.

Aside the (sometimes catastrophic) occurrence of sudden beam losses, also the impedance of narrow-gap collimators that are required for mitigating detector backgrounds is a major limitation to achieving high beam currents [35, 36]. The detector backgrounds are discussed in more detail in the next section.

More than ten FCCIS team members, from CERN, CEA, DESY and INFN, including several doctoral students and postdocs, were sent to KEK and contributed to the SuperKEKB accelerator restart and beam dynamics studies in the first half of 2024.

Figure 4: SuperKEKB achieved beam-beam parameters as a function of beam current [37].

4.3 Detector backgrounds in SuperKEKB

Beam backgrounds are another key challenge of SuperKEKB. During the SuperKEKB and Belle II designs, it had already been estimated that several Belle II subdetectors would be exposed to near-tolerable backgrounds at peak luminosity. The most vulnerable subdetectors are the Time of Propagation (TOP) particle ID system and the Central Drift Chamber (CDC). Since the start of SuperKEKB commissioning with a fully assembled Belle II detector in 2019, several dedicated beam background studies have been performed. Typically, the measurement starts with a single-beam configuration, where only one ring is filled with beam. By changing the number of bunches, beam gas and Touschek backgrounds can be disentangled during beam decay measurements when the injection is stopped. By repeating this measurement for the LER and HER, one can extract the background sensitivities for each sub-detector separately. Next, by extrapolating the single-beam backgrounds to the collision study when both beams are filled, we subtract the single-beam contribution from the observable and estimate the luminosity-related background sensitivity [38].

We use several dedicated Monte Carlo (MC) simulation tools to predict beam backgrounds at different machine settings and to investigate possible mitigation measures. For the simulation of beam gas and Touschek scattering, we first use the Strategic Accelerator Design (SAD) software developed at KEK. In the next step, the lost particles in SAD are transferred to Geant4 for further simulation. A realistic description of the geometry of the detector and accelerator tunnel is used to simulate the resulting electromagnetic showers and secondary particles produced inside and outside the detector. The observed data/MC ratios are generally within an order of magnitude of unity and are then used to scale the MC predictions for future beam parameters.

Unfortunately, with the machine lattice considered in the original machine design without the crab-waist scheme, the target beam currents will be difficult or even impossible to reach because of the short beam lifetime (< 10 min) due to the narrow dynamic aperture [33]. At present, the details of the machine lattice and beam parameters required to achieve the target SuperKEKB luminosity of

Figure 5: SuperKEKB vertical emittances as a function of bunch current in 2022 [37]. Red dots refer to the LER, blue ones to the HER.

Figure 6: SuperKEKB vertical specific luminosity in 2022 as a function of bunch current product [36]

$6 \times 10^{35} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ are too uncertain to make a reliable background prediction. Therefore, we focus on estimating backgrounds for intermediate beam parameters (i.e. $\beta_y^* = 0.6 \text{ mm}$) that are feasible with the current machine setup, which should allow to reach a luminosity of $2.8 \times 10^{35} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [38]. The resulting background composition for all Belle II sub-detectors is shown in Fig. 7. It should be noted that these simulations do not consider the crab-waist scheme, resulting in conservative background estimates. According to preliminary, separate SAD-only simulations, the crab-waist scheme is expected to reduce Belle II beam backgrounds by at least a factor of three at $\beta_y^* = 0.6 \text{ mm}$, if simulation-optimised

collimator settings can be achieved experimentally.

Figure 7: Estimated Belle II background composition for predicted beam parameters for a luminosity of $2.8 \times 10^{35} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Each column is a stacked histogram. The red numbers in rectangles are detector safety factors.

4.4 Cavity Reverse Phase Operation

FCC-ee and the recently approved EIC in the United States may use Reverse Phase Operation (RPO) [at CERN also called counterphasing] of the radiofrequency (RF) cavities [39, 40], in order to maintain optimum RF coupling for varying beam currents and RF voltages. So did an earlier version of SuperKEKB, where much higher beam currents had still been considered.

For RPO, the cavities are divided into groups with different RF phases [41]. The RPO allows a higher RF voltage/cavity than if all cavity phases were aligned. A high cavity RF voltage also avoids further reduction of the optimum loaded- Q value, corresponding to no RF reflection, which is the lower the larger the beam loading.

Thanks to these characteristics, RPO enables a substantial simplification of the FCC-ee RF system. In particular, it would avoid the use of single-ell 400 MHz cavities at the Z energy. Without such a mode of cavity operation the RF coupling of the two-cell FCC-ee cavities would have to change by a factor of several 100 between Z pole and $t\bar{t}$ energies, which appears extremely challenging.

RPO was successfully tested at the former KEKB [42], where the synchrotron frequency (f_s), which depends on the total RF voltage, was measured for several SC cavity configuration. Figure 8 shows f_s versus V_c , the total RF voltage of the HER generated by the SC and the normal-conducting ARES cavities.

The RPO with 7 normal-phase cavities and 1 reverse-phase cavity, “(7 - 1)”, and a voltage of 1.56 MV per cavity (red solid circles), resulted in almost the same measured f_s as that of 8 in-phase cavities with 1.18 MV per cavity (blue solid triangles). Therefore, the RPO scheme worked as expected. Behavior and stability of the (7 - 1) RPO were examined for beam currents up to 1.2 A, which is about the maximum value considered for FCC-ee. The RPO was used in the usual high-luminosity operation of KEKB during six days and it operated stably, without any problem. The KEKB tests demonstrated that RPO works well even under high beam-loading conditions

Figure 8: KEKB HER synchrotron tune measured for several SC cavity configurations. The RPO of the (7 - 1) case with 1.56 MV / cavity yielded about the same f_s as for 8 in-phase cavities with 1.18 MV / cavity [42]. [Originally published in Progress of Theoretical and Experimental Physics, 2013, 3, 03A006 © T. Abe et al., 2013. Published by Oxford University Press on behalf of the Physical Society of Japan.]

5 Conclusions and Outlook

With support from the FCCIS programme, progress has been made on the verification of a number of FCC-ee key performance enabling techniques. Optics tuning and correction tools were synergetically developed and tested at ESRF-EBS and PETRA III, together with experts from the light source community. Optics measurements based on single-bunch turn-by-turn BPM data were also explored at SuperKEKB. Experimental verification of resolution of the state-of-the-art BPMs were performed. Resonant depolarization studies were undertaken at KARA. Detector backgrounds at SuperKEKB were analysed. No showstoppers were detected in any of these areas. On the other hand, a number of challenges still remain. These include the final focus alignment and accurate prediction of beam dynamics performance in a unique regime governed by the interplay of impedance, beamstrahlung [43], beam-beam resonances, and machine errors [44]. The latter can be addressed by advances in simulation software while factoring in further experience from SuperKEKB and, potentially, DAΦNE.

Acknowledgements

This report benefited from material provided by, and discussions with, Tessa Charles, Bastian Haerer, Jacqueline Keintzel, Simone Liuzzo, Lukas Malina, Elaf Musa, Katsunobu Oide, Dmitry Shatilov, and Mikhail Zobov.

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